

Scalability and GPU Acceleration of MPACT Microapps on TACC: Method of Characteristics and Coarse Mesh Finite Difference

Wesley Lao^{1,*}, Aaron Graham², Braden Pecora^{1,2}, Micah Best², Cole A. Gentry¹, Benjamin Collins²,
Kevin Clarno¹

¹University of Texas at Austin, Austin, Texas, United States;

²Veracity Nuclear, Lenoir City, Tennessee, United States

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20804207

ABSTRACT

Strong scalability with OpenMP and the acceleration with data center graphics processing cards were studied on microapps mimicking the method of characteristics and coarse mesh finite difference solvers in MPACT. Scaling studies and memory profiling were performed on two and three dimensional test problems for modeling pressurized water reactors using the computing resources at the Texas Advanced Computing Center. Several single-node architectures were evaluated, including Nvidia, Intel, and AMD CPUs with Nvidia and Intel GPUs, to assess the viability of an accelerated build of the Virtual Environment for Reactor Applications targeting workstations representative of practical industry use. Further, results suggest what architecture such a workstation should have.

Keywords: MOC, CMFD, Microapp, Scaling, GPU

1. INTRODUCTION

VERA [1] is the primary product of the Consortium for the Advanced Simulation of Light Water Reactors (CASL), and has been demonstrated to accurately model centuries-worth of operational data from modern light water reactors (LWRs), including Watts Bar Units 1 and 2 [2, 3, 4, 5]. VERA provides high-fidelity multiphysics simulation capabilities for complex LWR reactor physics phenomena such as CRUD-Induced Power Shift (CIPS) and Pellet-Clad Interaction (PCI) [6, 7, 8]. However, this fidelity comes at a significant computational cost: modeling a single 18-month fuel cycle can require roughly 16 hours of runtime across thousands of Central Processing Unit (CPU) cores on leadership-class systems. In contrast, most industry codes are designed to run on workstations with far lower computational capabilities and fidelity. Such tools often use simplified representations of phenomena like CIPS and PCI and must compensate with conservative design margins to ensure safety and reliability.

To bridge this gap in computational infrastructure, the most expensive components of the MPACT code [9], the full-core neutronics solver in VERA, must be accelerated. Recent advancements in Graphics Processing Unit (GPU) cards open the possibility of storing large data structures in Video Random Access Memory (VRAM). To analyze the capability of a GPU compute node to run VERA, Veracity Nuclear [10] has developed standalone executables mimicking individual solvers within MPACT, which we refer to as “microapps”.

In this paper, we examine the performance of the method of characteristics (MOC) and coarse mesh finite difference (CMFD) microapps on several single-node architectures and the effects of available algorithmic choices. To explore several architectures, we used computational resources at the Texas Advanced Computing Center (TACC) [11], including Lonestar6 (LS6), Vista (VST), and Stamepde3 (ST3). This gives us access to CPUs from Intel, AMD, and Nvidia, as well as GPUs from Nvidia and Intel, which respectively use the CUDA and SYCL programming models. The full list of single-node architectures tested is summarized in Table I.

*wesley.lao@austin.utexas.edu

Table I. Single-Node Architectures Tested on TACC

System (Queue)	CPU (Microarchitecture)	GPU (Microarchitecture)
LS6 (gpu-a100)	EPYC 7763 (Zen3)	A100 PCIe (Ampere)
LS6 (gpu-h100)	EPYC 9454 (Zen4)	H100 PCIe (Hopper)
LS6 (NuclearEnergy)	EPYC 9754 (Zen4)	—
VST (gg)	Grace (ARM Neoverse V2)	—
VST (gh)	Grace (ARM Neoverse V2)	GH200 (Hopper)
ST3 (h100)	Xeon Platinum 8468 (Sapphire Rapids)	H100 SXM5 (Hopper)
ST3 (pvc)	Xeon Platinum 8480 (Sapphire Rapids)	Data Center GPU Max 1550 (Xe-HPC)
ST3 (spr)	Xeon CPU Max 9480 (Sapphire Rapids HBM)	—

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Scalability Metrics

We restrict ourselves to single-node architectures to mimic performance on industrial workstations. We are interested in the strong scalability of each microapp and the maximal viable level of parallelization. Strong scaling is concerned with the performance on a problem of fixed size n as the number of processors p increases. As we use more processors, we would desire the time to solution (the so-called “wallclock time”) to be the perfectly divided by p . Strong scalability describes how close to ideal the observed speedup is [12]. We define the speedup s as the ratio of the baseline wallclock time to the parallel wallclock time.

$$s(n, p) = \frac{t(n_0, p_0)}{t(n, p)} \quad (1)$$

where n and n_0 are the parallel and baseline problem size, respectively, and p_0 is the number of processors in the baseline case. We consider the serial case as our baseline ($p_0 = 1$). Since wallclock time is expected to be proportional to the amount of work per processor, we define the workload w as the quotient of the total problem size and the number of processors.

$$w(n, p) = \frac{n}{p} \quad (2)$$

We can further generalize the speedup by defining the parallel efficiency η as the ratio of the baseline node-time per unit problem size to the parallel node-time per unit problem size, which is equivalent to the speedup multiplied into the ratio of the parallel workload to the baseline workload.

$$\eta(n, p) = \frac{np_0 t(p_0, n_0)}{n_0 p t(p, n)} = \frac{w}{w_0} s(n, p) \quad (3)$$

Note that this quantity is equal to one if all of the work is perfectly divided amongst the processors and the communication costs are zero. However, we expect to see a level of parallelization at which the increase in communication overhead is greater than the reduction in work per processor, leading to a decrease in speedup. We are interested in finding the optimal workload that corresponds to the greatest speedup. We can estimate this workload by running a strong scaling study for a small enough n such that we achieve the maximal speedup.

$$w^* \approx \frac{n}{p^*(n)}, \quad p^*(n) = \operatorname{argmax}_{p \in P} s(n, p) \quad (4)$$

For GPUs, we generally do not desire less than maximal parallelism. Instead, we are interested in quantifying the speedup provided by the GPU over the alternative. At small problem sizes, we expect the data movement between host and device to dominate, leading to speedup less than one. However, for n large enough, the CPU work time

will be much greater than the data movement cost, giving a large speedup. We now define the GPU speedup as the speedup over the optimally parallelized CPU wallclock time $t_{CPU}(n, p^*(n))$, where $p^*(n)$ is estimated from the w^* found from the strong scaling study. Due to this data movement cost, there is likely a critical problem size for which this speedup is one, which we will consider the minimal GPU-viable problem size. Note that this depends upon the entire node, rather than something inherent to the GPU itself.

$$s_{GPU}(n) = \frac{t_{CPU}(n, p^*(n))}{t_{GPU}(n)} \approx \frac{t_{CPU}(n, \lceil n/w^* \rceil)}{t_{GPU}(n)} \quad (5)$$

where $\lceil \cdot \rceil$ denotes taking the ceiling operation. The critical problem size and the card VRAM then defines a *viability envelope* in which GPUs provide a speedup greater than one. We currently limit the scope to single-GPU architectures. Offloading computation to both OpenMP threads and GPUs is handled with Kokkos [13, 14].

2.2. Test Problems

For each scaling study, we execute five runs for each algorithm setting and thread count to account for stochastic variations in runtime. We did not observe outliers due to page faults or other errors and thus take the median time over the five runs to be $t(n, p)$. The thread counts are iterated over the set

$$P = \left\{ p \mid p = 2^k, k \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}, p \leq p_{max} \right\} \cup \left\{ p_{max}, \frac{p_{max}}{2} \right\}$$

The second subset allows us to capture the performance with single-socket and dual-socket thread counts, since the TACC nodes considered in the study have dual-socket motherboards and some CPUs did not have a core count equal to a power of two.

2.2.1. Method of characteristics

For strong scaling, our baseline is a 2D (axis-normal) slice of a small reactor core with 7 energy groups, 16 azimuthal directions, and 3 polar directions, called “Mini-core”. Mini-core has 62,160 rays and uses the cross sections from the C5G7 benchmark [15], but has a custom geometry based on tiling 21 7x7 assemblies with full symmetry. For GPU testing, we use three different geometries: a single pin cell, a 7x7 assembly from Mini-core, and Mini-core. We then create larger problems by duplicating those base domains 2^k times, so that we create a problem with $2^k n$ rays. In the OpenMP comparison, we use $\lceil 2^k n/w^* \rceil$ threads. The three geometries allow us to compare problems with differing ray lengths. Mini-core has 5 times the ray count and length compared to the 7x7 assembly, which itself has 7 times the ray count and length as the single pin cell. We have the option to sort the rays, either with short or long rays first. Sorting can minimize wait time on the GPU by marching along rays of similar length.

2.2.2. Coarse mesh finite difference

For strong scaling, our baseline is a 2D slice of benchmark problem 5a from [16] (5a-2d). Problem 5a is a 3D model of Watts Bar Unit 1 with no thermal-hydraulic feedback. This problem has a scattering matrix with a number of nonzeros (NNZ) of 60,515,019. For GPU testing, we create cubic arrays of N^3 pin cells, $N \in \{N \mid N = 2^k, k \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}\}$, and vary the number of groups g among four values for which we have cross sectional data $g \in \{8, 51, 69, 252\}$. We then create scattering matrices for each (N, g) pair that will fit in memory. Since the NNZ is expected to grow with the cube of N , it is more difficult to maintain w^* . We use the thread count that corresponds to the optimal workload or the maximum available processes if the former would exceed the maximum.

3. RESULTS

3.1. OpenMP Scalability

Figure 1 reports the strong scaling wallclock times, speedups, and parallel efficiencies, respectively, for MOC and CMFD with OpenMP parallelism. These estimates are summarized in Table II. Note that the t_{min} metric is the

minima of the curves from the top row of Figure 1. Unsorted rays resulted in greater efficiency across all CPUs, with sorted rays only providing improvement for high thread counts on the Grace Superchip, Xeon Platinum 8480, and Xeon CPU Max 9480. To the best of our knowledge, this behavior might be due to changes in memory access patterns between ray-indexed data and spatially-indexed data (e.g., cross sections), but the exact cause is unknown at the time of writing.

Table II. Minimal wallclock time (seconds, lower is better) and optimal workloads (lower is better) for MOC (rays/thread) on Mini-core and CMFD (NNZ/thread) on 5a-2d across tested CPUs.

CPU	MOC		CMFD	
	t_{min}	w^*	t_{min}	w^*
EPYC 7763	54.87	485.6	397.7	1.513e7
EPYC 9454	39.30	647.5	86.23	1.891e6
EPYC 9754	47.01	485.6	123.8	1.891e6
Grace	33.20	431.7	73.41	1.891e6
Xeon Platinum 8468	37.22	647.5	174.0	1.891e6
Xeon Platinum 8480	40.00	647.5	123.2	1.261e6
Xeon CPU Max 9480	43.09	555.0	187.0	1.891e6

3.2. GPU Acceleration

Figure 2 reports the GPU wallclock times and speedup for the MOC and CMFD microapps on the tested GPU nodes. For MOC, we observed decreasing speedup with increasing ray count when the rays are short. For small ray counts, the CPU runtime increases by only the communication cost. However, the GPU requires additional data movement, which could not be offset due to the small workload per ray. The difference in overhead is shown by CPUs outperforming their respective GPUs on problems with many short rays. Once the CPU becomes processor-limited ($\sim 10^5$ rays), the GPUs were all able to maintain a speedup greater than 1 with further increases in problem size. Thus, GPU acceleration should only be considered for MOC problems with small counts of short rays or large counts of long rays. Fortunately, the latter is likely to be the case for users modeling the entire reactor core.

Figure 3 reports the wallclock times and speedup for different ray sort orders for MOC on the Mini-core geometry. In contrast to OpenMP, we observed that sorting the rays by length resulted in a expected performance increase. However, the speedup was only significant for small ray geometries and the speedup for the Mini-core geometry was negligible. The cost of sorting the rays is not included in the wallclock times, but since sorting complexity is $O(n \log n)$, sorting is expected to be much more expensive than the observed speedup for the Mini-core geometry. Note that we do not consider parallel sorting algorithms in the scope of this study. The maximal and mean wallclock times and speedup for each GPU and sort order on the Mini-core geometry are reported in Table IV.

For CMFD, we observe three regions of behavior. For the smallest problems ($NNZ < 10^4$), there appears to be a floor for wallclock time, likely due to communication overhead. For a middle class of problems ($NNZ \in [10^4, 10^6]$), the wallclock clock time increases slowly, corresponding to a small increase in data movement cost without saturating the GPU. For large problems ($NNZ > 10^6$), the GPU becomes saturated, causing runtime to increase more rapidly. In the last regime, the Nvidia GPUs showed almost-constant speedups with further increases in problem size. The Data Center GPU Max 1550 (DCM 1550) performed at least 10 times worse than other GPUs on CMFD, pointing to possible optimizations to be made in the SYCL backend. Table III summarizes the performance of each tested GPU node. For calculating the mean metrics, we perform a support vector regression, which is presented as the trend line in Figure 2, and integrate the regressor. This is to account for the data being biased towards the smaller problem sizes and for the variability due to different problem geometries. Since the A100 card had less memory, its mean metrics are biased towards smaller problem sizes. Note that the DCM 1550 has 128 GB of memory, but using more than 64 GB requires exposing both tiles on the card. In practice, better performance was achieved by exposing only one tile in the “flat” hierarchy mode, giving the card an effective memory of 64 GB for these problems.

Figure 1. Strong Scaling Results for MOC and CMFD. For MOC, “none”, “short”, and “long” sort orders are shown with solid, dotted, and dashed lines, respectively.

4. CONCLUSIONS

We have presented results for OpenMP scalability and GPU viability for accelerating MOC and CMFD microapps. Nvidia GPUs provided about 10 times speedup on CMFD and core-scale MOC problems. However, limited VRAM and data movement overhead creates a viability envelope for GPU problem sizes. Ray sorting was found to be not efficient for single run use cases, but could provide benefits when the sorted ray order can be reused.

Figure 2. GPU Speedup Results for MOC and CMFD. For MOC, the single pin, 7x7, and Mini-core geometries are shown with triangles (\blacktriangle), squares (\blacksquare) and circles (\bullet), respectively.

Table III. Maximal and Mean GPU wallclock time (seconds, lower is better) and speedup (higher is better) for MOC on Mini-core and CMFD. We also report card memory and bandwidth (higher is better).

GPU	Memory (Bandwidth)	MOC				CMFD			
		t_{max}	t_{mean}	S_{max}	S_{mean}	t_{max}	t_{mean}	S_{max}	S_{mean}
A100 PCIe	40 GB HBM2 (1.6 TB/s)	697.6	371.5	7.899	4.160	3.332	1.963	31.42	13.625
H100 PCIe	80 GB HBM2e (2.0 TB/s)	367.8	201.0	6.540	5.310	2.919	2.276	15.64	4.785
GH200	96 GB HBM3 (4.0 TB/s)	329.3	179.4	4.947	3.785	1.620	1.271	26.08	7.110
H100 SXM5	96 GB HBM3 (3.4 TB/s)	431.5	244.7	7.795	5.586	2.171	1.717	22.74	12.586
DCM 1550	64 GB HBM2e (3.3 TB/s)	549.9	291.1	5.269	4.582	626.5	478.2	0.335	0.034

For problems within the GPU memory budget, emphasis should be placed on acquiring Nvidia cards with large VRAM and bandwidth. The Grace-Hopper Superchip was the most performant option for both microapps. For GPU-invisible problems, the Grace Superchip had the best peak OpenMP performance, and the EPYC 9454 had the best off-peak OpenMP performance. Future work will include acceleration of subchannel and conduction modules mimicking the thermal-hydraulics algorithms of CTF [17].

Figure 3. GPU Ray Sorting Results for MOC. Single pin, 7x7, and Mini-core geometries are shown with triangles (\blacktriangle), squares (\blacksquare) and circles (\bullet), respectively. Regressors for the “none”, “short”, and “long” sort orders are shown with solid, dotted, and dashed lines, respectively.

Table IV. Maximal and Mean wallclock time (seconds, lower is better) and speedup (higher is better) for MOC with different sort orders on Mini-core.

GPU	None		Short				Long			
	t_{max}	t_{mean}	t_{max}	t_{mean}	s_{max}	s_{mean}	t_{max}	t_{mean}	s_{max}	s_{mean}
A100 PCIe	697.6	371.5	802.2	400.8	1.213	0.970	799.2	400.0	1.209	0.970
H100 PCIe	367.8	201.0	384.3	202.0	1.112	1.012	386.2	202.2	1.103	1.013
GH200	329.3	179.4	310.9	165.5	1.174	1.089	316.1	166.9	1.168	1.086
H100 SXM5	431.5	244.7	441.1	237.7	1.127	1.026	441.8	228.5	1.156	1.078
PVC	549.9	291.1	527.2	271.6	1.134	1.079	531.3	271.9	1.142	1.082

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors acknowledge the Texas Advanced Computing Center (TACC) at The University of Texas at Austin for providing computational resources that have contributed to the research results reported within this paper. URL: <http://www.tacc.utexas.edu>. The authors acknowledge Veracity Nuclear for funding the research reported within this paper. URL: <https://veracitynuclear.com>. This material is based upon work supported by the U.S. Department of Energy, Office of Science, Office of Science Small Business Innovative Research program, under Award Number DE-FOA-0003417.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. A. Turner, K. Clarno, M. Sieger, R. Bartlett, B. Collins, R. Pawlowski, R. Schmidt, and R. Summers. “The Virtual Environment for Reactor Applications (VERA): Design and architecture.” *Journal of Computational Physics*, volume 326, pp. 544–568 (2016). URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0021999116304156>.
- [2] A. Godfrey, B. Collins, K. S. Kim, J. Powers, R. Salko, S. Stimpson, W. Wieselquist, K. Clarno, J. Gehin, S. Palmtag, et al. “VERA benchmarking results for watts bar nuclear plant unit 1 cycles 1-12.” In *Physics of Reactors 2016: Unifying Theory and Experiments in the 21st Century*, PHYSOR 2016, pp. 3983–3997. American Nuclear Society (2016).

- [3] A. Godfrey and F. Franceschini. “Watts Bar Nuclear Unit 2 Startup Experience.” Technical report, Oak Ridge National Laboratory (ORNL), Oak Ridge, TN (United States) (2020).
- [4] G. Mangham, A. Godfrey, and J. Eller. “VERA Benchmarking of PWR Startup and Steady State Operation.” In *Proceedings of the CASL Technical Symposium, ANS 2020 Winter Meeting, Chicago, IL, USA*, pp. 15–19 (2020).
- [5] A. Godfrey and B. Collins. “VERA neutronics high-fidelity benchmark for a modern PWR core design.” In *Proceedings of the international conference on physics of reactors-Physor 2022*, pp. 202–213 (2022).
- [6] B. Collins, R. Salko, K. Clarno, A. Wysocki, J. Galloway, B. Okhuysen, D. Andersson, C. d. M. M. Sociedad Nuclear Mexicana (SNM), and I. U. S. American Nuclear Society (ANS), La Grange Park. “Whole core Crud-induced power shift simulations using Vera.” In *Proceedings of the international conference on physics of reactors-Physor 2018* (2018).
- [7] R. Salko Jr, T. Lange, E. Tatli, B. Collins, D. Pointer, W. Gurecky, S. Slattery, and A. Manera. “Development of a crud induced localized corrosion analysis capability in vera.” Technical report, Oak Ridge National Laboratory (ORNL), Oak Ridge, TN (United States) (2020).
- [8] E. E. Davidson, A. T. Godfrey, K. E. Royston, T. M. Pandya, S. C. Henderson, and T. M. Evans. “Validation of light water reactor ex-core calculations with VERA.” *Nuclear Technology*, **volume 208**(5), pp. 794–810 (2022).
- [9] A. Graham, E. W. Larsen, B. Collins, B. M. Kochunas, and S. Stimpson. “MPACT 4.4 Theory Manual.” Technical report, Oak Ridge National Laboratory (ORNL), Oak Ridge, TN (United States) (2023).
- [10] “Veracity Nuclear, LLC.” <https://veracitynuclear.com/>.
- [11] “Texas Advanced Computing Center (TACC) The University of Texas at Austin.” <https://tacc.utexas.edu>.
- [12] V. Eijkhout, R. van de Geijn, and E. Chow. *Introduction to High Performance Scientific Computing* (2016).
- [13] H. C. Edwards, C. R. Trott, and D. Sunderland. “Kokkos: Enabling manycore performance portability through polymorphic memory access patterns.” *Journal of Parallel and Distributed Computing*, **volume 74**(12), pp. 3202 – 3216 (2014). URL <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0743731514001257>. Domain-Specific Languages and High-Level Frameworks for High-Performance Computing.
- [14] C. R. Trott, D. Lebrun-Grandié, D. Arndt, J. Ciesko, V. Dang, N. Ellingwood, R. Gayatri, E. Harvey, D. S. Hollman, D. Ibanez, N. Liber, J. Madsen, J. Miles, D. Poliakoff, A. Powell, S. Rajamanickam, M. Simberg, D. Sunderland, B. Turcksin, and J. Wilke. “Kokkos 3: Programming Model Extensions for the Exascale Era.” *IEEE Transactions on Parallel and Distributed Systems*, **volume 33**(4), pp. 805–817 (2022).
- [15] M. A. Smith, E. E. Lewis, and N. Byung-Chan. *Benchmark on deterministic transport calculations without spatial homogenisation: A 2-D/3-D MOX Fuel Assembly Benchmark*. Nuclear Energy Agency, Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, Paris (2003). OCLC: 1039251119.
- [16] A. T. Godfrey. “VERA Core Physics Benchmark Progression Problem Specifications, Revision 4, CASL Technical Report.” Technical Report CASL-U-2012-0131-004, Consortium for Advanced Simulation of Lightwater Reactors (2011).
- [17] J. Salko, M. Avramova, A. Wysocki, B. Hizoum, A. Toptan, J. Hu, N. Porter, T. S. Blyth, C. A. Dances, A. Gomez, C. Jernigan, J. Kelly, and A. Abarca. “CTF Theory Manual: Version 4.3.” Technical Report ORNL/SPR-2022/2494, Oak Ridge National Laboratory (ORNL), Oak Ridge, TN (United States) (2022). URL <https://www.osti.gov/biblio/1994732>.